

A NOVEL TECHNIQUE FOR DATA HIDING IN COLOR PALETTED IMAGES

Lale Akarun*, Nilay Özdilek*, B. Uygur Öztekin**

* Bogazici University, Istanbul, Turkey

Tel: +90 212 263 15 40 X 1858

Fax: +90 212 287 24 61

e-mail: akarun@boun.edu.tr

** University of Minnesota, USA

ABSTRACT

The size of an uncompressed image depends on the resolution of the image and the number of colors in it. Gray-scale images typically contain 256 or fewer gray levels. In a color image, the color of each pixel is represented by three bytes, one each for red, blue and green. This leads to a potential of more than 16 million colors. However, the eye can discern only about 10,000 distinct colors. Moreover, common images usually contain fewer colors. Many images, therefore, contain much fewer colors, which form a palette. Many file formats treat the information in such a color image as a table containing the palette and individual pixels as pointers to that table. In this paper, a novel technique for hiding data using the palettes of color images is proposed. The technique can be implemented without interfering with the image data, by using unused entries or visually indistinguishable colors in the image palette.

1. INTRODUCTION

True color images represent the color of each pixel with three bytes. This leads to more than 16 million colors. However, due to practical reasons and economy of storage, many applications reduce this color range to a limited palette. This palette is a table which contains the red, green and blue components of the colors used in the image. The image body consists of pointers to that table.

The palette size is often a power of two, and more commonly, 256. However, the color image often contains even fewer distinct colors. In that case, either some entries in the palette are never referenced, or two or more entries are identical and used interchangeably. This fact has suggested that the empty palette entries can be used for embedding data in images: Suppose that palette entries 0 and 1 contain the same color. Every time that color is used in the image, either of the palette entries

can be referenced, resulting in a binary string as long as the number of times that color is used in the image. The appearance of the image is unaffected since palette entries 0 and 1 are identical.

We have investigated the feasibility of that approach and implemented the technique. Our results show that the data embedded images are identical in appearance to original ones. We are working on ways to make the technique robust to common image operations.

2. IMAGES AND COLOR PALETTES

The rgb color coordinate system used in color images is a device-oriented color coordinate system. It is based on the three phosphor primaries adopted by the National Television Systems Committee (NTSC). This color coordinate system is not visually uniform; that is, color differences computed by the Euclidean distance are not perceptually meaningful.

Furthermore, many practical applications reduce the number of colors in a color image by a process called color quantization. The most common algorithm used in application programs is the "median-cut" algorithm. This algorithm iteratively partitions the color space with planes perpendicular to the color axes and passing through the medians of the data [1].

The palettes formed as a result of these operations consist of colors which may be redundant or which may be perceptually indistinguishable. We have investigated the validity of this statement to find out the potential for application of the new data hiding technique. Table 1 summarizes our findings. We have examined images of different types: face images and outdoor scenery. In general, indoor scenes and face images have more unused palette entries while outdoor scenery have a fuller color palette. It is observed that

the majority of images contain a number of unused palette entries. However, in some images, all palette entries may be utilized. For those images, we have investigated other possibilities: Some palette entries may be visually indistinguishable. A distance measure that represents visual differences is ΔE , defined as:

$$\Delta E = [(L_1^* - L_2^*)^2 + (a_1^* - a_2^*)^2 + (b_1^* - b_2^*)^2]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

where $L^*a^*b^*$ is the CIELAB color coordinates [2]. In general, a ΔE value of 3 or less indicates that the two colors are visually indistinguishable. It is observed from Table 1 that the number of visually indistinguishable colors is usually large. Another possibility for creating empty palette entries is mapping the least used palette entries to the closest color. This was found to be appropriate in the last three images in Table 1. Since these images contain a lot of detail, the color change in the least used entries was found to be acceptable.

3. DATA EMBEDDING IN COLOR IMAGES

Assume that the highest peak in the image histogram corresponds to C, and $h(C)$ is the

number of times that color is used; i.e, number of times that palette entry is referenced.

Let the number of unused colors be M. If an N-ary string ($N \leq M$) is to be embedded, the last N-1 entries of the palette are set to C. The i^{th} element of the N-ary string can now be represented by the i^{th} identical palette entry. Let the string to be embedded be S. According to this algorithm, the m^{th} occurrence of C will be replaced by palette entry S(m).

To make this algorithm as robust as possible and as undetectable as possible, the best value for N is two, i.e. S a binary string. This way, only one free entry in the palette is needed and only one palette entry is changed.

We have implemented this algorithm with paletted images of different sizes. Figure 2 shows the results of our algorithm. Figure 2(a) shows the original image, scenery with buildings 3. We have embedded a binary string of length 12,224 in that image using the unused palette entry. Figure 2(b) shows the result of reducing five palette entries. A 6-ary string of the same length is embedded in Figure 2(b).

Table 1: Utilization of palettes

Image	# unused palette entries	# reduced palette entries
Face image 1	14	31
Face image 2	8	33
Face image 3	3	16
Scenery with buildings 1	0	11
Scenery with buildings 2	3	6
Scenery with buildings 3	1	5
Scenery with fall foliage 1	0	1
Scenery with fall foliage 2	0	8
Scenery with fall foliage 3	0	1

Figure 1 (a) Original Image; (b) Image after reduction of 20 unused and similar colors

Figure 2 (a) Original Image; (b) After reduction of 5 colors, a 6-ary string of length 12,224 has been embedded

4. EFFECTS OF COMMON IMAGE PROCESSING OPERATIONS

In order for the watermark to be robust to cropping, we repeatedly embedded the string as many times as possible into the image. As the string gets shorter, the number of times the string is being embedded increases, making the watermark more robust to cropping.

In order to be able to identify the start and stop of the embedded string within the image, we used a start string of 8 characters and a control string of 8 characters. The start string SS is a string which should not be in S itself. The control string CS has the value $\text{length}(S)$ in binary form.

In order to be able to find the most used palette index, we search for the colour which is identical to the colour in the 256th palette entry. This way, we don't lose the most frequent colour used during the encoding operation, even if it is not the peak of the histogram any more (e.g. after a cropping operation).

When searching for the watermark string, the image is scanned to find the start string.

Whenever the start string is found, the indices are held in temporary locations (ind_SS), until no more copies of the start string are found. The 8 characters after the start string is the control string. These are converted to decimal numbers and held in temporary locations (ind_CNC).

The string is then extracted using following iteration :

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for  $i=0$  to  $\text{length}(\text{ind\_SS})$  {
  if  $((\text{ind\_SS}(i+1) - \text{ind\_SS}(i)) = \text{ind\_CNC}(i))$  {
     $S = \text{string from } \text{ind\_CNC}(i)+8 \text{ to } \text{ind\_SS}(i+1)$ 
  }
}

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Whenever a control string conflicts with the indices, then the next possible string is being examined.

However, the algorithm is not robust to colour enhancements and other image processing techniques which alter the palette heavily or even make the palette obsolete.

Figure 3 Both images contain the same string. (a)original, (b) cropped.

5. CONCLUSION

We have suggested a technique for embedding data in paletted color images. The technique does not change the image itself in any way and is based on the use of unused or similar entries in the palette. We have investigated the feasibility of that approach by studying common images. Upon implementation, our results show that the data embedded images are identical in appearance to original ones. We are working on ways to make the technique robust to common image operations.

The data capacity of this approach is usually very high, however, as the length of the string to be embedded increases, the robustness of the watermark to cropping decreases. If the string is long, the watermark can only be extracted after cropping in areas where colour C is used very frequently.

The algorithm is easy to implement. However, if the technique is known to the misuser, it is also easy to remove the watermark from the image.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Heckbert, "Color image quantization for frame buffer display", *Comp. Grap.*, vol.16, no. 3, pp. 297-307, July 1982
- [2] M.D. Fairchild, *Color Appearance Models*, Addison-Wesley, 1998.